

Query by Example in Remote Sensing Image Archive Using Enhanced Deep Support Vector Data Description

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Abstract—This article studies remote sensing image retrieval using kernel-based support vector data description (SVDD). We exploit deep SVDD, which is a well-known method for one-class classification to recover the most relevant samples from the archive. To this end, a deep neural network (DNN) is jointly trained to map the data into a hypersphere of minimum volume in the latent space. It is expected that similar samples to the query are compressed inside of the hypersphere. The closest embedding to the center of the hypersphere is related to the most relevant sample to query. We enhance deep SVDD by injecting the statistical information of data to the DNN by means of additional terms in the cost function. The first enhancement method takes advantage of covariance regularization of batches of the training set to penalize unnecessary redundancy and minimize the correlation between the different dimensions of the embedding. The second method involves unlocking the hypersphere’s predefined center while preventing network divergence during training. Therefore, two parameters are designed to control the importance of the drifting of the center and the importance of a fixed predefined center (convergence), respectively. This has been implemented by considering the average of batches of embedding in each iteration as the updated center. This pushes irrelevant samples away from query samples, making data clustering easier for the DNN. The performance of the proposed methods is evaluated on benchmark datasets.

Index Terms—Deep neural network (DNN), deep support vector data description (SVDD), EuroSAT, one-class classification, query by example in earth observation, remote sensing (RS) image retrieval.

I. INTRODUCTION

REMOTE sensing (RS) imagery is a valuable data source for Earth Observation to measure different physical

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The source code is available at <https://github.com/omid-ghozatlou/Query-by-Example-Using-SVDD>

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properties on earth [1]. Thanks to the advances in earth observation technology, both the quantity and quality of RS images are drastically growing. According to a study [2], about a hundred small satellites (Smallsats) were launched in 2013 and almost 200 in 2014. Since then the numbers have been increasing with over 300 launches in 2017 and 2018. It is noteworthy that only in 2020, the number of Smallsats launched worldwide amounted to 1202, which represented a more than threefold increase in comparison to the smallsats launched a year earlier. As a result, unconsciously, we have entered an era of big earth data, also called RS Big Data [3], [4]. Big earth data provides great opportunities and plays an important role in many applications such as fusion-oriented RS image processing [5], [6], [7], geolocalization [8], [9], and disaster rescue [10].

On the other hand, there are some processing challenges due to computational complexity, large volume, and large variety. Efficient information management, data mining, and interpretation methods are critical for making full use of huge RS data [11]. Image retrieval from RS Big Data has attracted researchers’ interest for decades as one of the most fundamental and important tasks in RS Big Data mining [12].

Content-based image retrieval (CBIR) from RS Big Data aims to discover the most relevant samples of archive data and has wide applications. According to the survey [12], the existing RS image retrieval methods can be grouped into four categories.

- 1) Conventional content-based RS image retrieval: This category (also called query by example [13]) is based on three modules including feature representation, feature indexing, and similarity measuring. In query by example, information can be extracted in the form of features from both the query image and archive images and then used to find similar features. This can be implemented as single-label [14] or multilabel [15], [16] (for more complex data) CBIR. For instance, Shao et al. [17] proposed multilabel RS image retrieval based on a fully convolutional network to address the poor retrieval performance for complex RS images.
- 2) Hashing-based RS image retrieval [18], [19]: This category is more common for large-scale RS image retrieval. To achieve this, feature reduction techniques have been adopted. To pursue a thorough reduction, feature hashing maps the high-dimensional feature vector to a low-dimensional binary feature vector. This enables

not only saving the storage space needed for feature representation but also lifting the computational speed of feature comparing. Liu et al. [20] exploited a generative adversarial network and proposed a new CBIR method including a deep feature learning model and an adversarial hash learning model to increase the retrieval efficiency. However, this method needs a large amount of supervised information for training. Later, to overcome this limitation, they proposed metahashing [21] by developing a self-adaptive convolution block that could achieve high retrieval performance with a few labeled training samples.

- 3) Cross-modal RS image retrieval [22], [23], [24]: This category takes advantage of other kinds of data sources. It refers to retrieving results corresponding to the query from a different modality, which is more flexible and practical [25]. For instance, Cheg et al. [26] proposed a novel cross-modal network that exploits the attention and gate mechanisms to establish a direct relationship between RS images and their paired text data.

Although in recent decades cross-modal (query by sketch, text, keywords, tags, audio, etc.) RS image retrieval got more attention, it has some limitations due to the scarcity of datasets and the complicated characteristics of RS image data.

- 4) Interactive RS image retrieval [27], [28], [29]: Experts in the image processing community employ active learning (AL) methods to iteratively boost the retrieval performance by taking the user's feedback into account [30]. AL leverages an expert oracle to label the most informative samples from the unlabeled archive. The training set is then updated by incorporating these labeled informative samples. As a result, the query strategy to find the most informative samples is the core of any AL method. In [31], a novel AL method is presented, in which the query strategy is based on three criteria: uncertainty, diversity, and density of images in the archive. As opposed to [31], which combined different heuristic query strategies, Barz et al. [32] proposed an information-theoretic AL, which is based on maximizing the mutual information between the predicted relevance of the images and the expected user feedback regarding the selected batch.

As a summary, any kind of CBIR systems [31], [33] essentially consists of (at least) two modules: 1) a feature extraction module that derives a set of features for characterizing and describing images and 2) a retrieval module that searches and retrieves images similar to the query image. The studies of the second module are limited to similarity distance measurements and indexing techniques. Nevertheless, there are recent studies that improve the distance measurement used as a similarity criterion [34], [35]. As an instance, Ye et al. [36] proposed a retrieval method based on weighted distance and basic features of CNN. In addition, Ye et al. [35] proposed a new retrieval scheme based on fuzzy class membership of images to reduce the overall search time.

Because retrieval performance is dependent on the capability and effectiveness of feature extraction techniques in describing and representing images, recent RS literature has focused

primarily on feature extraction techniques. As a result, feature extraction plays an important role to increase the accuracy of the learned model and reducing the dimensionality of data by removing redundancy. In this study, we focus on the first module (i.e., enhancement of the feature extraction techniques in image retrieval) and present recently published articles in this domain in the following. Before deep learning (DL) came to the attention of the image processing community, feature extraction methods mainly relied on handcrafted features [37], such as color histogram, texture descriptors, or the representations generated by encoding local features, such as bag of visual words [38]. However, the performance of the handcrafted features is limited as they can extract only low-level information and are not able to represent the image statistics in an accurate manner [11], [39].

Thanks to the capability of mimicking a nonlinear function of deep neural networks (DNN), these models are able to capture the essential characteristics of images [11], [12]. The embedding in latent-space layers of DNN models can be taken as high-level features to comprehensively represent the visual content of RS images [12]. As a result, DL provides the most common and useful feature extraction methods with many applications in RS image processing. The main issue with using DL is that it is greedy for data to optimize a massive number of parameters. If a DNN model is to be trained in a supervised manner, a large amount of labeled data is required. In the RS Big Data era, we can easily collect a large amount of raw data, but accurately labeling oversized data becomes challenging because there exist many kinds of RS images compared with the fixed RGB format of natural images in the computer vision domain. For this reason, experts study unsupervised DL methods to tackle the data labeling problem. However, these methods can have wildly inaccurate results and need enhancement and improvement to achieve more accurate and reliable results. In recent studies, many enhancement techniques have been proposed to help or guide DL models. Physics-aware DL, combining feature extraction approaches with DNN, modifying the network architecture, and designing cost functions are some examples of these techniques, which are further described in the following.

In RS, experts pay attention to extracting physical information in different wavelength bands of multispectral (MS) images. In addition to the spectral features, spatial features provide important information on data [40]. For example, Chaudhuri et al. [41] provide a method to capture spatial detail. Therefore, a graph convolutional network (GCN) with pairwise similarity constraint is proposed to address RS image retrieval.

Generally, different shape features help to make up for each other's defects. As a consequence, the combination of multiple hand-crafted features often presents stronger representation ability and benefits in improving RS image retrieval [42]. For example, Devulapalli and Krishnan [43] proposed a new feature set by integrating handcrafted features at detailed scales and deep features to improve the system's efficiency.

In recent years, several studies have developed the DNN algorithms by modifying the network architecture or loss function to improve feature extraction [44], [45], [46]. Also, many specific objective functions have been proposed to train CNNs for RS image retrieval [47], [48], [49], [50], [51]. For example,

Cao et al. [52] have provided an enhancement method for RS image retrieval by exploiting a triplet loss in learning discriminative deep features. Recently, Sumbul and Demir [53] have provided a DL-based multitask learning (MTL) for CBIR on DLRSC [54] and BigEarthNet [55] archives. They propose a novel enhancement of MTL by defining two novel loss functions to ensure the plasticity and stability conditions of the whole learning procedure independently of the number and type of tasks.

Our work also contemplates the design of a new loss function that can cluster similar features (or embeddings) in the latent space. The main idea is used for anomaly detection, which is an unsupervised problem by nature. Image retrieval such as anomaly detection can be considered a one-class classification that can be conducted by any kind of classification method. Therefore, this can be a clever solution to solve the scarcity of labeled training data. For instance, Mou et al. [56] proposed a data enclosing-ball minimizing autoencoder (AE) for change detection. As well as, Xu et al. [57] suggested a bidirectional GAN-based one-class classifier for network intrusion detection in which only normal data samples are used for training and both normal and anomalous data samples are used during testing to identify anomalous samples in the test set. In line with this research, we selected and utilized a one-class classification methodology. However, we enhanced the strategy by creating a new cost function to model the MS data for the RS image retrieval task.

In this article, we exploit and modify the idea of deep support vector data description (SVDD) [58] for RS image retrieval. Deep SVDD is inspired by kernel-based one-class classification and uses a neural network to map most of the data network representations into a hypersphere. Therefore, a DNN is jointly trained to map the data into a hypersphere of minimum volume in the latent space. It is expected that relevant (similar) samples to the query are concentrated inside of the hypersphere and irrelevant samples (outliers or ambiguous) are moved away from the hypersphere. The closest embedding to the hypersphere center corresponds to the most relevant sample to the query. We modify the network's objective function to take advantage of the statistical information of data. We employ the covariance regularization in [59] to prevent an informational collapse in which the encoder produces constant or noninformative vectors. It penalizes unnecessary redundancy of the embedding in the latent space. In addition, we propose a novel cost function to minimize the volume of the hypersphere by unlocking the hypersphere's predefined center while preventing network divergence during training. It allows the hypersphere center to be free to compress the relevant samples as much as possible while driving irrelevant ones away. Our main contributions are the following.

- 1) To the best of our knowledge, this article is the first to study deep SVDD (or any one-class classification method) for CBIR. Due to not being a fully supervised approach, less labeled data (only samples of one class) are needed for training and the samples of other classes can be unknown.
- 2) Enhancing the cost function with an additional covariance term to minimize the correlation between dimensions in

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the methodology of image retrieval using SVDD.

the latent space becomes especially relevant when dealing with high-dimensional data.

- 3) Providing a novel cost function by unlocking the hypersphere's predefined center and considering the average of embeddings over a batch in each iteration as a moving center while preventing network divergence during training.

Furthermore, we investigate the relationship between the entropy of images and the image retrieval performance of the enhanced methods. The methodology is explained in Section II. Section III presents the experiments in more detail. The results are discussed in Section IV and conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. METHODOLOGY

This section is presented in three main phases, namely: pre-training, training, and inference. Given a query sample, the goal is to find the most relevant samples in the archive. To achieve this, we exploit statistical information and physical properties to aid the DNN. The main idea of the proposed method is to map the network representation of the training dataset into a hypersphere with query samples falling inside and other class samples falling outside of it. The most relevant sample is the closest embedding to c , the hypersphere's center. Fig. 1 shows the block diagram of the methodology of image retrieval using deep SVDD. In the first phase, we exploit and train an AE with all training samples.

A. Pretraining

Let X and X' be the batch of query samples and the archive samples including all classes, respectively. X' is used only in the inference phase and does not interfere with the pretraining or the training phases. In the first step, the AE consists of the symmetrical encoder ϕ and decoder θ and is trained by X . The objective of the AE is to optimize the network weights W_ϕ and W_θ by minimizing the reconstruction distance that is defined by

$$\min_{W_\phi, W_\theta} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left\| x_i - \theta(\phi(x_i; W_\phi); W_\theta) \right\|_2^2 \quad (1)$$

where X is the batch of query sample and each sample is denoted x_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where n is the size of the batch.

We find c by feeding query samples to the pretrained network and then calculating the mean values of the network's outputs, as formulated in the following equation:

$$c = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \phi(x_j; W_\phi) \quad (2)$$

where m is the number of samples of the query in the training set.

B. Training

In this phase, we employed three different scenarios for training the network. The baseline (deep SVDD) is presented in the first scenario. Two enhanced versions of deep SVDD, namely, covariance-aware SVDD (CA-SVDD) and drifting-center SVDD (DC-SVDD), are discussed in the second and third scenarios, respectively.

1) *Deep SVDD*: In this section, the deep SVDD [58] is presented in detail. The training phase aims for volume minimization in feature space by finding a data-enclosing hypersphere of the smallest size. The classifier network (pretrained encoder) is jointly trained to map the data into the smallest hypersphere and learns useful feature representations of the query class samples. The classifier network's weights W are initialized by the weights of the pretrained decoder W_ϕ . The network's objective is to optimize the network weights W by minimizing the distance of embedding from c which is defined by the following equation:

$$\min_W \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(x_i) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \sum_{k=1}^K \|W^k\|_F^2 \quad (3)$$

where the first term is defined by

$$D(x_i) = \|\phi(x_i; W) - c\|_2^2 \quad (4)$$

and the second term is a weight decay regularizer on the network parameters W with hyperparameter λ , where $\|\cdot\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm.

$D(x)$, the distance of each test sample from c in latent space, can be used as a measure for ranking the test samples. The lowest score represents the most relevant (normal) sample and the highest score represents the most ambiguous (anomalous).

2) *Covariance-Aware SVDD*: We modify the cost function of the decoder in (3) by an additional term. Let annotate each vector of the network's output $y_i := \phi(x_i; W) = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d]$, where d is the dimension of the network's output. The images are processed in batches, and we denote $Y = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n]$ a batch composed of n vectors of dimension d of embeddings coming out of the network. The goal of this term is to minimize the sum of the squared off-diagonal coefficients of the covariance matrix of Y . The covariance matrix, $\Sigma(Y)$ is defined as

$$\Sigma(Y) := \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})(y_i - \bar{y})^T$$

where $\bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i$. (5)

The overall loss function is a weighted average of all three terms

$$\min_W \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(x_i) + \frac{\nu}{d} \sum_{i \neq j} [\Sigma(Y)]_{i,j}^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \sum_{k=1}^K \|W^k\|_F^2 \quad (6)$$

where x_i is each sample of the query class and ν is a parameter for controlling the importance of the second term in the loss.

3) *Drifting-Center SVDD*: In the second scenario, the hypersphere's center is updated in each iteration of the training process. Therefore, the first term of the proposed cost function in (3) $D(x)$ is extended to two terms

$$D'(x_i) = a \|\phi(x_i; W) - \tilde{c}\|^2 + b \|\tilde{c} - c\|^2 \quad (7)$$

where a and b weight for the importance of the first and second terms, respectively. The parameter \tilde{c} allows for the drifting of the hypersphere's center. It represents the average of batches of embedding in each iteration and is calculated by

$$\tilde{c} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \phi(x_i; W) \quad (8)$$

where n is the number of batches in each epoch. The first term in (7) allows the center to be drifted by \tilde{c} during the training process. On the contrary, the second term penalizes how much this one drifts from the initial center obtained in the pretraining phase to prevent divergence of the network.

C. Inference

The last phase is to discover and retrieve the most similar samples in the archive, X' . After the training phase, we feed all samples of X' to the trained network and then rank the samples based on distances from c . The process of selecting similar samples is defined by

$$\Gamma_k := \{x'_i : [\|\phi(x'_i; W) - c\|_2^2 < \|\phi(x'_j; W) - c\|_2^2]\}$$

s.t. $i \neq j$ and $|\Gamma_k| = k$ (9)

where Γ_k denotes the set of the k retrieved samples. Also, two different samples of archive are denoted x'_i and x'_j for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, l$, where l is the number of the samples in archive.

III. EXPERIMENTS

A. Dataset

We study the performance of the method on the EuroSAT [60] dataset. The benchmarked EuroSAT dataset has been used for recent studies in the RS field, in particular for the image classification task. EuroSAT has been collected by Sentinel-2 A satellite and presented in 2018. We employed both EuroSAT RGB bands and MS bands for training and testing the network. The benchmark covers 13 spectral bands and comprises ten classes with a total of 27 000 and 25 000 labeled and georeferenced images for RGB and MS, respectively. The dataset includes sections of 64×64 pixels following ten semantic classes: Annual Crop (A.C.), Forest, Herbaceous Vegetation (H.V.), Highway, Industrial, Pasture, Permanent Crops (P.C.), Residential, River, and Sea or Lake.

In addition, for comparison to prior methods of CBIR in RS, we employed a well-known dataset called, UC Merced (UCM) Land Use dataset [61]. It consists of images characterizing 21 categories (i.e., classes) selected from aerial orthoimagery. Each category includes 100 images that were downloaded from the USGS National Map of some U.S. regions. Each image in the archive is a section of 256×256 pixels following 21 classes: agriculture, airplane, baseball diamond, beach, buildings, chaparral, dense residential, forest, freeway, golf course, harbor, intersection, medium-density residential, mobile home park, overpass, parking lot, river, runway, sparse residential, storage tanks, and tennis courts.

B. Model Configuration

In the original study, [58], LeNet, a well-known convolutional neural network, has been employed to map input data into a hypersphere. LeNet consists of three convolution modules, including a convolutional layer followed by leaky Relu activation, batch normalization, and finally a max-pooling layer. After convolution modules, a fully connected layer of d units has been employed for classification. For fair comparison to prior work, we adopt the same network architecture.

C. Training Details

For the training phase, we use stochastic gradient descent to optimize the parameters of the neural network. The number of epochs for pretraining and training the networks is set to 50 and 100, respectively. The batch size is set to 128 by considering the computational power and shared memory of the GPU. Since the dataset is not the same as in the original study [58], the hyperparameter of weight decay λ is set to the optimal value $\lambda = 10^{-6}$ through investigating the average of the results of fivefolds cross validation for three different values. The network has been trained on an NVIDIA Quadro GV100 GPU with 32 GB memory. Since EuroSAT dataset consists of ten semantic classes, there are ten different queries-by-example setups (in the case of using the UCM dataset, there are 21 setups). Therefore, the network is separately trained using the samples of the class of query in each setup. EuroSAT dataset is split randomly into training and test sets with ratios of 80% and 20% (this ratio is 60% and 40% for the UCM dataset). To apply CBIR, the training set of the archive is used for selecting query images, while images were retrieved from the test set. In this case, the training set consists of 2400 and 60 samples of the class of the query in EuroSAT and UCM archives, respectively. Therefore, all 5400 and 420 test samples consisting of all classes are considered a repository (archive) for image retrieval in EuroSAT and UCM datasets, respectively. Since the size of the training set of UCM is not sufficient, the data augmentation technique is exploited to make the network's weight optimization feasible. It is worth emphasizing that in each setup the class of query changes while the test set and other parameters of the algorithm are the same for all setups. In addition, in order to fairly compare the results of each one-class classification setup, the random seed for pretraining initialization is fixed (set to 1) for all setups to make the evaluation reproducible and avoid result changes in case of multiple executions of the algorithm.

D. Evaluation

We evaluate all three proposed methods on different classes of interest as queries. Based on the relevant/irrelevant samples, RS image retrieval can be considered a binary classification problem [62]. Therefore, model performance is quantified using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve metric (AUROC). This performance indicator is usually employed for anomaly detection or binary classification [63], [64]. Since the study has an application in CBIR, we also assess the performance of the methods with evaluation metrics that are commonly used in the literature. Precision, Recall, and F-score are the common evaluation metrics in image retrieval tasks [39], [65]. The Precision is defined as the percentage of correctly retrieved (true positive) images TP out of the total number of retrieved images N_r as follows:

$$\text{Precision} := \frac{\text{TP}}{N_r} \quad (10)$$

and the Recall represents the percentage of correctly retrieved images out of the total number of relevant images present in the dataset N_q and is calculated as

$$\text{Recall} := \frac{\text{TP}}{N_q}. \quad (11)$$

The F-score is computed from the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, as formulated in the following equation:

$$F_\beta := \frac{(\beta^2 + 1) \cdot \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\beta^2 \cdot \text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (12)$$

where, depending on the parameter β , the F-score gives more importance to Precision or Recall. In this study, we have used $\beta = 1, 2$, which is most common in the literature.

E. Existing Methods for Comparison

In the RS literature, we cannot find so many studies of CBIR using DL. Various methodology concepts (hash-based or AL methods) and different goals (time series image retrieval, multilabel image retrieval) or dataset types (cross-modal data including text, sound, etc.) make the number of related studies more limited. However, it is necessary to compare the proposed method with the existing CBIR methods in RS in order to assess its effectiveness and robustness. Therefore, in addition to the baseline (SVDD), we employ TCAL [31], which has got a lot of attention in RS society because of its high retrieval accuracy. The TCAL implementation in python is exploited to train on the EuroSAT dataset and compare it with our method. In order to achieve the results of the article, the AL iteration is set to 10 according to the published paper and the results of TCAL are the averages of 30 trials per each query of a class. Also, we evaluate our method using three different random seeds and compare the average of them. In addition, we chose another study CBP-ResNet that has been published in 2020 and made the code publicly available. Wang et al. [66] introduced a second-order pooling named compact bilinear pooling (CBP) into DNN for RS image retrieval. All the parameters are set according to the original paper. As well as, another recent RS image retrieval study exploited Gabor Channel Attention ResNet

Fig. 2. Top 60 most relevant samples are retrieved from the test set when the query is A.C., Forest, H.V., Highway, Industrial, Pasture, P.C., Residential, River, and Sea or Lake, respectively. The first two rows show the results of deep SVDD for $d = 128$. The two middle rows are related to the CA-SVDD method with $\nu = 1024d$ and the last two rows indicate the results of DC-SVDD when $a = 1$ and $b = 1000$ (the last column in Table III).

(GCA-ResNet) and the split-based deep feature transform network [67] is chosen to compare with our methods. To have a comprehensive comparison, the performance of all methods is compared on the same dataset (UCM) and both EuroSAT (RGB) and EuroSAT (MS) datasets.

IV. RESULTS

The results are described in three parts. Section IV-A describes the qualitative results of each method. Section IV-B presents the AUROC quantitative evaluation results. Section IV-C comprises a quantitative evaluation of each method using Precision, Recall, and F-score. Finally, in Section IV-D a comparison with prior works is presented.

A. Qualitative Evaluation

The 60 most relevant samples corresponding to different queries are shown in Fig. 2. The top-left sample is the most relevant and the score is increasing from left to right. The first two rows show the results of deep SVDD for $d = 128$. We can see that the image retrieval works well for only the Sea/Lake class, which has uniform distribution and the lowest average of entropy. By looking at the most relevant samples for other classes, we recognize that all samples are uniform and textureless. That means the network is able to learn only uniform samples and demonstrates the need for a more elaborated cost function to learn more complex features. In contrast, most of the retrieved samples using an additional covariance term are more complex

TABLE I
AUROC VALUES IN % FOR A SPECIFIC NORMAL CLASS OF EUROSAT

Avr. Ent.	Normal Class	SVDD		CA-SVDD		
		$d = 128$	$\nu = \frac{d}{4}$	$\nu = d$	$\nu = 16d$	$\nu = 1024d$
5.780447	A.C.	56.62	54.06	53.32	54.41	31.4
3.69844	Forest	89.99	92.02	94.15	95.54	94.95
5.655537	H.V.	40.41	41.73	42.12	44.49	58.54
5.941791	Highway	44.93	44.26	43.99	44.02	56.75
6.83639	Industrial	59.06	64.03	65.92	73.83	87.58
4.906731	Pasture	71.25	71.76	72.71	74.66	80.29
6.18885	P.C.	35.26	36.27	36.57	36.51	37.18
6.12598	Residential	36.17	53.59	64.77	83.29	89.81
5.391266	River	60.78	60.37	60.74	61.05	61.29
2.384127	SeaLake	95.82	95.88	96.03	95.98	95.67
	Average	59.03	61.4	63.03	66.38	69.35

The first column compares the average entropy of each class. The results for the classes with more than 20% improvement have been highlighted. The third column shows results using SVDD and the next columns correspond to the result using covariance term (CA-SVDD) with different values of ν . The best and second-best results are bold and underlined, respectively.

samples much closer to the human expectation for each class. The results for $\nu = 1024d$ are shown in the two middle rows of Fig. 2. As reported in Table I, the performance of the model for Industrial and Residential queries improved more than for other classes. Also, the most relevant samples of these two classes are totally correct. In addition, retrieved samples of Forest and Pasture are much more accurate than using deep SVDD. However, some samples of Forest are retrieved for a query of Pasture, which might be because of the similar spatial structure. The last two rows indicate the results of DC-SVDD when $a = 0.001$ and $b = 1$. They show that the additional drifting center term improves the image retrieval of almost all classes. The samples of the A.C., P.C., and River are retrieved more reliably than with

Fig. 3. Embedding of test samples using (a) SVDD, (b) CA-SVDD, (c) DC-SVDD for query A.C., Pasture, and Residential in the first, second, and third rows, respectively.

previous methods. Also, the most relevant samples of Industrial and Residential classes are still totally correct. In addition, image retrieval for Highway queries has improved, despite there being some samples of River in the top 60 most relevant samples. The similar spatial texture of these two classes leads the network to consider them the same class. It is worth mentioning that there are some incorrectly retrieved samples. More specifically, one can observe some retrieved Forest samples for the Sea query and A.C. for the P.C. query. Unfortunately, no method can correctly retrieve samples of H.V. query.

In order to understand the behavior of the proposed methods, we also evaluate each method by looking at the embedding of the test set. Since the visualization of the embedding with 128 dimensions is impossible, we use the t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding [68] algorithm in Python for the visualization of data in 2-D. Since it can find the nonlinear connections in the data, it is more popular compared to other dimensionality reduction methods. Fig. 3 shows the embedding of test samples using deep SVDD [see Fig. 3(a)], CA-SVDD [see Fig. 3(b)], and DC-SVDD [see Fig. 3(c)] for query A.C., Pasture, and Residential in the first, second, and third rows, respectively. We observe that both proposed enhanced methods, CA-SVDD and DC-SVDD, change the feature latent space to cluster different classes. SVDD [see Fig. 3(a)] compressed all (both relevant and irrelevant) samples by minimizing the hypersphere volume. On contrary, CA-SVDD [see Fig. 3(b)] maps the test samples to a broader area in order to facilitate the clustering. Similarly, DC-SVDD [see Fig. 3(c)] adjusts the feature latent space to relocate the irrelevant samples away from the query samples. In order to take advantage of spectral information from Sentinel-2 satellite images, we also use the EuroSAT dataset with all MS bands. Each band has its own set of physical characteristics that can be used for a variety of applications. This makes the network extract not only spatial information but also MS properties. The results of training and testing the network using all bands of the dataset are considerable. Fig. 5 explains the behavior of the

network for classes that have similar structures when training and testing the network on all MS bands. The 60 most relevant samples for query Industrial using deep SVDD, CA-SVDD, and DC-SVDD are described in the first row. The Residential samples (red square) are retrieved wrongly because most of them have similar structures to Industrial samples. SVDD recovered 25 samples belonging to Residential while CA-SVDD and DC-SVDD retrieved 10 and 4 samples wrongly. The visualization of the feature space of the test set including Industrial as query and Residential provides better insights into the performance of methods. For this purpose, two-dimensional representations of the feature space using SVDD, CA-SVDD, and DC-SVDD are shown in the second row. We can see that both modified methods, CA-SVDD and DC-SVDD, change the feature space to separate Residential samples from the query samples close to the center. We observe that Residential (irrelevant) samples are not concentrated towards the center, resulting in better retrieval performance for both modified techniques.

In order to analyze the importance of each term of DC-SVDD, we set different values for a and b in (7). Fig. 4 shows the embedding of test samples of A.C. (blue points) versus other classes. The first row represents the embedding using deep SVDD, the second row corresponds to the DC-SVDD method when $a = 1$ and $b = 0$ [removes the second term in (7)]. Although the embeddings in the two first columns are compressed by minimizing the distance of embedding point clouds from the initial center, normal samples close to the center are surrounded by outliers. The next rows represent the results of DC-SVDD by increasing the importance of the second term setting $b = 1$. The results of this method when $b = 1$ are described in the third and last rows for $a = 0$ and $a = 0.001$, respectively. In both last rows, outliers (irrelevant samples) are clearly farther from the center than in the first two columns. By looking at the third-row scatter plots, we realize that setting $a = 0$ produces elongated structures in the feature domain, as by removing the first term of (7), there is no term enforcing volume minimization. For this reason, we set $a \neq 0$ to force the embedding point clouds to the center. As a result, the last row's results show the value of combining both terms. By looking at the last row, we can see that not only are outliers pushed out as far as possible, but there is also a concentration of normal samples near the center.

B. Quantitative Evaluation Using AUROC

Table I compares the percentage of the AUROC values of test samples using CA-SVDD. The query class (class of query) of each setup is mentioned in the second column. In order to quantify the diversity of the classes, we calculate Shannon's entropy [69] of each image. In information theory, Shannon's entropy quantifies the amount of information in a variable and is used for the study of the theoretical foundation of DL [70]. The first column in Table I compares the average entropy of the samples of each class to present how complex (information content) the images of each class are. When we examine the values for each class more closely, we can see that the majority of the best and second-best values are presented in the two last columns. This means that increasing the importance of the

Fig. 4. Embedding of test samples of A.C. versus other classes. The first row presents the result of deep SVDD [58] and the next rows correspond to the DC-SVDD method when $b = 0$, $a = 0$, and $a = 0.001$.

Fig. 5. First row shows the 60 most relevant samples retrieved from the MS test set when the query is Industrial using SVDD, CA-SVDD, and DC-SVDD, respectively. The retrieved Residential samples are shown by the red squares. The related embeddings of the Industrial versus Residential class are shown using TSNE in the second row. (a) SVDD. (b) CA-SVDD. (c) DC-SVDD.

covariance term (ν) we introduce improves the AUROC values for almost all classes. In addition, the fact that all values in the last row (average of all classes' AUROC values) are higher than those in the third column demonstrates the importance of decorrelating the dimensions of the latent space by means of a covariance penalty.

As described in Table I, AUROC values of setups using Deep SVDD (column 3) for the lowest entropy classes, Forest (89.99%) and Sea (95.82%) are higher than for other classes. Thus, we observe that training the network on samples of classes with low entropy provides higher accuracy. In addition, the fact that modifying the loss function with covariance terms does not provide great improvement for these classes means that DNN can extract useful features and learn efficiently without additional covariance terms due to their limited information

content. However, when looking at complex classes (high average entropy), we can see that the largest improvement belongs to the Residential class (more than 53%), followed by the Industrial class (more than 28%), both of which have been highlighted in blue. The classes with a high average of entropy benefit more than other classes because modifying the loss function and adding the covariance term aids the DNN to extract more discriminative features by minimizing the correlation between dimensions of embedding.

Table II compares the results of AUROC values with different values of embedding's dimension. The second and third columns describe AUROC values using deep SVDD when $d = 32$ without additional cost term and with it, respectively. The next two pairs of columns are related to results for $d = 128$ and $d = 512$, respectively. The fact that all columns related to the

TABLE II
AUROC VALUES IN % FOR A SPECIFIC NORMAL CLASS OF EUROSAT

Normal Class	SVDD		CA-SVDD		SVDD		CA-SVDD	
	$d = 32$	$\nu = 16d$	$d = 128$	$\nu = 16d$	$d = 512$	$\nu = 16d$	$d = 512$	$\nu = 16d$
A.C.	61.46	75.2	56.62	54.41	62.17	64.64	62.17	64.64
Forest	90.07	93.8	89.99	95.54	90.63	94.36	90.63	94.36
H.V.	41.79	38.75	40.41	44.49	43.11	40.51	43.11	40.51
Highway	42.39	41.26	44.93	44.02	45.6	43.57	45.6	43.57
Industrial	67.06	63.21	59.06	73.83	47.37	54.43	47.37	54.43
Pasture	70.06	77.42	71.25	74.66	70.74	72.01	70.74	72.01
P.C.	37.16	62.23	35.26	36.51	40.31	43.54	40.31	43.54
Residential	30.36	49.16	36.17	83.29	37.7	52.73	37.7	52.73
River	58.29	54.05	60.78	61.05	60.49	60.17	60.49	60.17
SeaLake	95.25	95.31	95.82	95.98	95.77	95.64	95.77	95.64
Average	59.39	65.04	59.03	66.38	59.39	62.16	59.39	62.16

Each odd column (skip the first column with the names) shows the results using deep SVDD with different embedding's dimension and the next column corresponds to the results of CA-SVDD when $\nu = 16d$. The last row describes the average AUROC values of all classes.

TABLE III
AUROC VALUES IN % FOR A SPECIFIC NORMAL CLASS OF EUROSAT

Normal Class	SVDD	$a = 1$		$b = 1$	
		$b = 0$	$b = 0.001$	$a = 0$	$a = 0.001$
A.C.	56.62	50.2	58.7	<u>79.11</u>	85.67
Forest	89.99	85.54	91.23	88.08	95.14
H.V.	40.41	<u>53.69</u>	42.91	52.29	66.9
Highway	44.93	51.76	48.53	61.63	70.13
Industrial	59.06	35.28	45.72	80.84	<u>79.13</u>
Pasture	71.25	62.14	73.95	84.07	<u>81.87</u>
P.C.	35.26	54.47	54.97	<u>70.23</u>	71.8
Residential	36.17	<u>59.43</u>	46.24	51.14	84.69
River	60.78	58.93	64.53	76.27	<u>71.91</u>
SeaLake	95.82	68.39	96.12	89.62	89.47
Average	59.03	57.98	62.29	<u>73.33</u>	79.67

The first column describes the results of deep SVDD and the next columns correspond to the results of the drifting center with different values of parameters. The last row describes the average AUROC values of all classes. The best and second-best results are bold and underlined, respectively.

CA-SVDD show higher AUROC demonstrates the importance of the covariance term in the cost function. By looking closer to Table II, we witness improvement for classes A.C. and P.C. for $d = 32$ while the benefit decays with a further increase of d , with no improvement at $d = 128$. This is coherent with the fact that the covariance term boosts the efficiency of the representation in the latent space and makes adding further dimensions futile since it penalizes redundancy.

The results of the experimental evaluation with the drifting center of the hypersphere (DC-SVDD) are given in Table III. It is worth noting that a and b are the weighting parameters in (8). They control how much the center can be drifted in latent space during training. The results demonstrate that updating the hypersphere's center in each iteration leads to higher AUROC. These two parameters are chosen by trial and error. We analyzed the importance of the first term by setting the first term weight $a = 1$ and removing the second term ($b = 0$) and then increasing the value of b as can be seen in Table III (two columns with $a = 1$). Then we repeat this procedure for the second term and the results are given in the two last columns of Table III. By considering the fact that the average of embedding is very similar to c , the first term in (8) is not different from the (5) in the baseline (SVDD). Therefore, using only the first term (when $b = 0$) does not provide very different results from the deep SVDD [58]. This can be shown by the results in the third column when $a = 1$ and $b = 0$, which are quite similar to the results of deep SVDD in the second column. However, the second term provides helpful outcomes. The AUROC values for all classes are increased in the

TABLE IV
AUROC VALUES IN % FOR A SPECIFIC NORMAL CLASS OF EUROSAT

Normal Class	SVDD	DC-SVDD		SVDD		DC-SVDD	
		$d = 32$	$b = 100$	$b = 1000$	$d = 128$	$b = 100$	$b = 1000$
A.C.	61.46	66.05	84.78	56.62	59.6	85.67	
Forest	90.07	90.17	92.17	89.99	94.28	95.14	
H.V.	41.79	43.41	61.05	40.41	43.98	66.9	
Highway	42.39	40.99	61.41	44.93	45.66	70.13	
Industrial	67.06	76.14	84.02	59.06	86.62	79.13	
Pasture	70.06	76.39	83.24	71.25	72.09	81.87	
P.C.	37.16	51.98	79.41	35.26	47.91	71.8	
Residential	30.36	51.94	53.83	36.17	81.87	84.69	
River	58.29	69.09	78.19	60.78	66.37	71.91	
SeaLake	95.25	93.05	92.16	95.82	94.03	89.47	
Average	59.38	65.92	77.03	59.03	69.24	79.67	

The second column shows the results of deep SVDD $d = 32$ and the two next columns correspond to the results of DC-SVDD when $b = 100$ and $b = 1000$, respectively. Similarly, these results are shown in the last three columns for $d = 128$. For all experiments of DC-SVDD $a = 1$. The last row describes the average AUROC values of All classes.

two last columns. That means that increasing the importance of the second term (b) or reducing the importance of the first term (a) minimizes the distance between the average of the embedding and the center of the hypersphere in each iteration.

Table IV compares the results of AUROC values with different values of embedding's dimension using SVDD and DC-SVDD. The second column shows the results of deep SVDD $d = 32$ and the two next columns correspond to the results of DC-SVDD setting $a = 1$ for $b = 100$ and $b = 1000$, respectively. Similarly, these results are shown in the last three columns for $d = 128$. By looking at the average AUROC of all classes in the last row, we witness the enhancement of performance by increasing the importance of the second term in (7). The fact that all columns related to the DC-SVDD show higher AUROC demonstrate that unlocking the center during the training aids the DNN to extract more common features from query samples. Therefore, it facilitates clustering and improves the classification (in this study retrieval) performance.

In order to evaluate the effectiveness and robustness of the proposed methods on another dataset, we compare the results of AUROC values using the UCM archive. Table V compares the results of SVDD, CA-SVDD, and DC-SVDD for each class. In all methods, $d = 128$ and the parameter of the importance of covariance term $\nu = 1024d$ for CA-SVDD method. In addition, the parameters for CA-SVDD $a = 1$ and $b = 1000$. These values are chosen based on the high performance of experiments on EuroSAT. As can be seen, almost all of the best AUROC values are shown in the CA-SVDD or DC-SVDD. This demonstrates the enhancement of the proposed methods. DC-SVDD improves the average of AUROC values by more than 20% compared to the baseline (SVDD).

C. Quantitative Evaluation Using Precision, Recall, and F-Score

Table VI describes the values of Precision, Recall, F1, and F2 scores using SVDD with only visible bands (RGB) and all MS bands. The higher values of each measurement have been shown in bold numbers. We witness that most of the bold numbers belong to SVDD using all MS bands. As a result, MS data provide more information and the network learns better from almost all classes.

TABLE V
AUROC VALUES IN % FOR A SPECIFIC NORMAL CLASS OF UCM DATASET

#	Class	SVDD	CA-SVDD	DC-SVDD
1	Beach	39.56	53.02	42.68
2	Agricultural	53.02	83.33	93.77
3	Buildings	59.69	65.27	65.35
4	Forest	48.12	60.02	98.99
5	River	39.97	69.89	50.23
6	Harbor	63.27	78.33	99.55
7	Dense residential	49.03	65.37	39.67
8	Sparse residential	67.33	89.99	71.23
9	Freeway	39.97	75.66	90.17
10	Airplane	50.00	83.65	73.67
11	Baseball diamond	69.03	60.23	58.33
12	Chaparral	60.31	60.35	50.36
13	Golf Course	46.37	44.78	56.89
14	Mobile home park	40.35	41.67	54.97
15	Intersection	39.66	59.31	41.77
16	Medium residential	27.01	41.67	69.38
17	Overpass	38.95	36.33	67.33
18	Parking lot	38.95	95.55	93.67
19	Runway	37.21	71.33	91.67
20	Storage tanks	29.91	46.75	48.12
21	Tennis court	32.56	40.33	39.67
Average		46.20	62.99	66.55

The first column describes the results of deep SVDD and the next columns correspond to the results of CA-SVDD and DC-SVDD. The last row describes the average AUROC values of all classes. The best result for each class is highlighted in bold.

TABLE VI
PRECISION, RECALL, F1, AND F2 SCORES FOR RGB AND MS USING SVDD

Normal Class	RGB				Multispectral			
	Precision	Recall	F1	F2	Precision	Recall	F1	F2
A.C.	0	0	0	0	0	0.077	0	0
Forest	0	0.125	0	0	0.9	0.79	0.841	0.81
H.V.	0.05	0.013	0.021	0.015	0.15	0.087	0.11	0.095
Highway	0.05	0.005	0.009	0.006	0.1	0.09	0.095	0.092
Industrial	0.15	0.165	0.157	0.162	0.4	0.41	0.405	0.408
Pasture	0	0	0	0	0.05	0.11	0.069	0.089
P.C.	0	0.003	0	0	0	0.138	0	0
Residential	0.3	0.028	0.051	0.034	0.75	0.405	0.526	0.446
River	0	0	0	0	0	0.07	0	0
SeaLake	1	0.95	0.974	0.96	1	1	1	1

Precision is calculated for 20 retrieved images.

TABLE VII
PRECISION, RECALL, F1, AND F2 SCORES USING DC-SVDD AND CA-SVDD

Normal Class	$b = 1000$				d_{1024}			
	Precision	Recall	F1	F2	Precision	Recall	F1	F2
A.C.	0.7	0.565	0.625	0.588	0.15	0.018	0.032	0.022
Forest	1	0.787	0.881	0.822	0.5	0.672	0.573	0.629
H.V.	0.3	0.255	0.276	0.263	0.1	0.12	0.109	0.115
Highway	0.35	0.24	0.285	0.256	0.15	0.095	0.116	0.103
Industrial	0.85	0.427	0.568	0.474	0.8	0.453	0.578	0.496
Pasture	0.2	0.235	0.216	0.227	0.3	0.28	0.29	0.284
P.C.	0.65	0.273	0.385	0.309	0.05	0.003	0.006	0.004
Residential	0.9	0.557	0.688	0.603	1	0.615	0.762	0.666
River	0.75	0.35	0.477	0.392	0.1	0.035	0.052	0.04
SeaLake	0.25	0.41	0.311	0.363	1	0.922	0.959	0.937

Precision is calculated for 20 retrieved images.

Table VII comprises the values of Precision, Recall, F1, and F2 scores for methods DC-SVDD and CA-SVDD. The higher values of each measurement have been shown in bold numbers. The fact that all values are higher than those described in Table VI demonstrates the shortcoming of SVDD and the need for a more elaborated cost function. Also, it shows the benefit of additional covariance minimization terms and unlocking the hypersphere's center in the loss function. DC-SVDD does not provide any improvement for class Sea/Lake (lowest average entropy) and one can observe that SVDD without this relaxation can distinguish Sea samples from other classes easily. In addition, the covariance minimization does not improve image retrieval for the query of A.C. while drifting the center plays

a very important role to improve the Precision to 0.7. Both methods improve all criteria (Precision, Recall, F1, and F2 scores) for complex classes (highest average entropy), such as Industrial and Residential.

Fig. 6 shows values of Precision for each method versus the number of retrieved samples. We analyze the performance of the method regarding the number of retrieved images. It provides the different behavior of methods per number of retrieved images. We comprise as well the results of SVDD using all MS bands (MS-SVDD) and also the combination of the enhanced methods ($\nu = 1024$ $db = 1000$). By looking at the charts, we witness that both methods using CA-SVDD ($\nu = 1024$ d) and DC-SVDD ($b = 1000$) have higher Precision compared to SVDD (except for Sea query). As an example, Fig. 6(a) shows the Precision for A.C. and illustrates that SVDD and CA-SVDD are not able to recover the images correctly. In contrast, DC-SVDD and the combination of CA-SVDD and DC-SVDD methods ($\nu = 1024$ $db = 1000$) have more than 0.7 Precision. Fig. 6(b) shows the shortcoming of SVDD to correctly retrieve the samples of Forest. Since the two classes, Sea and Forest, have the lowest average entropy and similar spatial features (uniform distribution) and color features, some Sea samples are retrieved wrongly for Forest query (see Fig. 2 to find retrieved patches). However, the performance of the methods using MS-SVDD and DC-SVDD is considerably improved and CA-SVDD also performs better than SVDD.

Furthermore, we witness a negligible drop in Precision by increasing the number of retrieved. Fig. 6(c) demonstrates the benefit of the proposed enhanced methods (CA-SVDD and DC-SVDD) for such a complex query, Industrial. Although the Precision of the proposed enhanced methods decreased dramatically after 100 retrieved samples, they perform better than SVDD and MS-SVDD. Fig. 6(d) shows the high performance of DC-SVDD for P.C. We witness the decrease in the Precision after 20 retrieved samples for the P.C. query, which can also be observed in Fig. 2 since some A.C. samples are retrieved inaccurately. Fig. 6(e) demonstrates how the proposed enhanced methods improve the performance and stability (with respect to the number of retrieved images) for the Residential query (the second highest average entropy). Fig. 6(f) is related to the query class Sea (the lowest average entropy), which is the only class, wherein the SVDD performs well but DC-SVDD is not able to recover Sea samples. In contrast to DC-SVDD, CA-SVDD retrieve correctly the Sea samples such as SVDD and MS-SVDD.

D. Comparison With Prior Works

In this section, the results of the proposed methods are compared with the baseline and state-of-the-art methods in two parts, namely: Overall results and Per class results.

1) *Overall Results:* Table VIII lists values of Precision at 10, 20, and 40 retrieved from the archive and the average of them on all three datasets. The best and second-best results are marked in bold and underlined, respectively. As can be seen, the baseline (SVDD) cannot perform accurately on any dataset, and the average Precision value is less than 40%. However, both proposed

Fig. 6. Precision versus a number of retrieved images when the query is (a) A.C., (b) Forest, (c) Industrial, (d) P.C., (e) Residential, (f) Sea or Lake.

TABLE VIII

PRECISION AT 10, 20, AND 40 AND AVERAGE OF THEM ON ALL THREE DATASETS COMPARED WITH THE BASELINE AND STATE-OF-THE-ART METHODS

Method	Year	EuroSAT (RGB)				EuroSAT (MS)				UCM			
		AP	P@10	P@20	P@40	AP	P@10	P@20	P@40	AP	P@10	P@20	P@40
SVDD (baseline) [58]	2018	0.276	0.315	0.315	0.199	0.355	0.417	0.335	0.313	0.227	0.386	0.163	0.133
CA-SVDD (ours)	-	0.626	0.674	0.616	0.59	0.694	0.728	0.68	0.673	0.545	0.614	0.549	0.473
DC-SVDD (ours)	-	0.697	0.762	0.693	0.637	0.748	0.791	0.745	0.71	0.697	0.767	0.694	0.629
TCAL [31]	2015	0.678	0.733	0.684	0.619	0.661	0.71	0.645	0.629	0.683	0.755	0.698	0.597
CBP-ResNet [66]	2020	0.684	0.755	0.691	0.606	0.683	0.733	0.701	0.616	0.676	0.74	0.681	0.609
GCA-ResNet [67]	2021	0.705	0.781	0.72	0.616	0.725	0.781	0.728	0.666	0.695	0.773	0.697	0.616

The best and second-best results are marked in bold and underlined, respectively.

Fig. 7. Precision for different categories obtained by SVDD, CA-SVDD, DC-SVDD, TCAL, CBP-ResNet, and GCA-ResNet when the top 20 images are retrieved. The order of the class numbers is the same as Tables and for EuroSAT and UCM, respectively. (a) EuroSAT (RGB). (b) EuroSAT (MS). (c) UCM.

methods improved the performance by more than 25% and 35% using CA-SVDD and DC-SVDD, respectively. Prior works perform better than the baseline as most of the bold and underlined values are seen on the three last rows. Although GCA-ResNet outperforms other methods on the EuroSAT (RGB) dataset, DC-SVDD with less than 1% of average Precision performs well after GCA-ResNet. By looking at the results of EuroSAT (MS), we witness DC-SVDD outperforms other methods. It demonstrates the proposed methods take advantage of MS data and improve the retrieval performance by 5%. However, the state-of-the-art methods do not benefit from MS data as can be

seen that TCAL and CBP-ResNet perform similarly to both the RGB and MS data.

2) *Per Class Results*: Fig. 7 summarizes the results obtained by extracting the query images from all categories of EuroSAT (RGB), EuroSAT (MS), and UCM datasets, respectively. It shows the average of 30 trial Precision in the top 20 retrieved results for each category independently of others. As shown in Fig. 7(a), the performances of all methods vary in different categories. Both proposed DC-SVDD and CA-SVDD methods result in higher Precision for almost all of the categories compared to the baseline (SVDD). TCAL outperforms other methods

for the class of Highway (4). It might be the case that the AL strategy in this method improves the accuracy for classes with high class-wise separability. In greater detail, for difficult categories (highest average entropy), the Precision values obtained by the proposed CA-SVDD and DC-SVDD are much higher than by SVDD [e.g., for the categories Industrial (5) and Residential (8)]. This clearly shows the ability of the proposed method to overcome the problems related to difficult categories. For the very easy categories, e.g., Sea (10) or Lake, SVDD can perform well, whereas the DC-SVDD shows the lowest performance. GCA-ResNet and CBP-ResNet could efficiently retrieve the images of the H.V. (3) and River (9). However, DC-SVDD not only can retrieve effectively images of these classes but also the classes of A.C. (1), Forest (2), and P.C. (7).

The results of image retrieval Precision at 20 retrieved images on EuroSAT (MS) are shown in Fig. 7(b). As can be seen, the performances of the proposed methods for almost all categories are higher than the baseline. The only class of H.V. (3) got better performance using the GCA-ResNet by 18% higher than TCAL and DC-SVDD. We witness the improvement of performance using MS image data compared to RGB. This demonstrates that the proposed methods are suitable for the RS image retrieval task. In general, compared with SVDD, the proposed CA-SVDD and DC-SVDD methods can perform much better for almost all categories, indicating clearly the effectiveness of the proposed enhanced methods for CBIR or, in general, one-class classification tasks. In addition, Fig. 7(c) illustrates the results obtained by extracting the query images from all 21 categories of the UCM Land Use dataset. As we can see, both proposed methods outperform the baseline for all classes. CA-SVDD could achieve the highest performance for classes: river (5), sparse residential (8), and baseball diamonds (11). In contrast, GCA-ResNet and CBP-ResNet perform quite similarly for most classes and both methods have shown the best performance for classes: beach (1), mobile home park (14), intersection (15), and tennis court (21). TCAL has the highest performance for some classes such as chaparral (12), and mobile home (14). However, the Precision obtained by the proposed method DC-SVDD for complex classes such as freeway (9), medium residential (16), and storage tanks (20) is much higher than by TCAL and other two state-of-the-art works.

V. CONCLUSION

In this article, we have introduced two novel methods to guide DNN by considering statistical information of data. The first proposed method penalizes unnecessary redundancy and minimizes the correlation between different dimensions of embedding. The second method tries to minimize hypersphere volume considering the unblocking of the center of the hypersphere. This relaxation makes the clustering of data easier for DNN. Both proposed methods overcome the limitations of Deep SVDD in particular when the query belongs to a complex class. We have emphasized that these are very important advantages because the main objective of CBIR is to optimize the search with a minimum number of annotated images to find the most similar samples in the archive.

Moreover, we have introduced the use of deep SVDD for CBIR problems (particularly in the context of the query by example) in RS. The experimental performances of the proposed system were evaluated on an archive of 5400 images describing ten different categories for the EuroSAT dataset, and also, another well-known dataset UCM with 21 classes is employed to assess the effectiveness and robustness of the proposed methods. The results show that the proposed methods provide efficient image retrieval performance, largely surpassing the considered baseline method (SVDD). In addition, we evaluated the performance on MS data, attaining superior results as compared to RGB data. It is also worth noting that the proposed methods are independent of the considered DNN, and therefore, they can be used for any cost function to guide the DNN to achieve a superior representation of the data.

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